

Multi-proxy provenance approach towards understanding transport processes in aeolian environments: A case study from the Ili Basin, southeast Kazakhstan

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1. INTRODUCTION

Wind-blown dust deposits, commonly known as loess, are important terrestrial archives of past climate [1,2]. Identifying the origin (provenance) of loess sediments can help determine major dust transport pathways, thereby providing insight into atmospheric circulation patterns in the past. A range of provenance methods have so far been applied to identify the provenance of aeolian loess, including radiogenic isotope analysis (Sr and Nd), major and trace elements, and detrital zircon geochronology [e.g. 3, 4, 5]. Traditional geochemical analyses are often applied to bulk sediments and can lead to inconclusive results, while the U-Pb based detrital zircon approach for provenance is limited by the availability of sufficient detrital zircon grains in (mostly) fine-grained loess archives [6, 7,8]. In a recent study, we proposed a new methodological approach for provenance of quartz based on characterisation of naturally occurring lattice defect centres, namely E₁' and peroxy, in quartz crystals using electron spin resonance (ESR) technique [9]. These defect centres accumulate in quartz over thousand-to-million-year timescales as a result of heavy particle radiation in rocks [9, 10] and their concentration depends on the age and type of rock, thus acting as an indicator of the source area.

The new quartz provenance methodology using ESR was successfully able to differentiate fine-grained loessic (aeolian) quartz from across two Basins in Central Asia known to be derived from different source areas [9]. This novel method, along with luminescence sensitivity of quartz was also investigated on sediments down a long loess-palaeosol sequence in Tajikistan to better understand temporal variations in source in response to changes in climatic conditions [11]. The promising results from the application of quartz-ESR in provenance studies on aeolian environments shows great potential for this technique. However, this method has not yet been validated with other independent and more established geochemical and mineralogical provenance methods. In addition, the quartz-ESR based provenance method has until now only been used to distinguish loessic quartz from across two different Basins [9]. The ability of this new method to distinguish temporal variations in the source of loess deposits from within the same Basin remains unexplored.

Identifying the provenance of dust within a sedimentary Basin through time can help us better understand the processes and vectors of sediment transport within a sedimentary Basin, thus giving us an insight into

regional wind dynamics through time. In order to understand dust transport pathways in the past, we need to quantitatively and qualitatively assess present-day (modern) aeolian transport pathways. This brings us to the *first* question - can we quantitatively differentiate modern potential source areas within the Basin? And if so, can they be linked to modern (surface) dust deposits in the region? *Secondly*, can we look at the provenance of palaeodust deposits in the region to elucidate wind-dynamics in the region through time?

Towards this goal, the Ili Basin of southeast (SE) Kazakhstan provides an ideal study region for examining the potential link between the different source areas and the loess deposits draping its piedmonts (Fig. 1). Not only does the Basin contain extensive piedmont loess deposits, dune-fields and alluvio-fluvial outwash plains, but the tributaries of the Ili River which drain the Tien Shan mountains surrounding the Basin also cuts through a variety of rocks of different ages [12]. Recent back-trajectory models [13] for dust transport within the Basin suggest that supraregional westerly and northerly winds (the latter associated with the seasonal expansion and contraction of the Siberian high), as well as local katabatic winds, are responsible for transporting dust to the Ili Basin piedmonts, thus suggesting a link between proximal source areas and loess deposits in the region. Moreover, climatically this region lies at the intersection of two major northern hemisphere climate subsystems: the mid-latitude Westerlies and Siberian High-pressure system [14, 15], which present the possibility of multiple vectors for aeolian transport, and therefore multiple sediment sources through time. This setting ensures an excellent natural laboratory for investigating sediment provenance to understand aeolian dynamics in the region both past and present.

Figure 1. Regional setting and location of study sites in the Ili Basin of SE Kazakhstan. The surface sediments were collected from various locations in the Moyunkum and Taukum dunefields, proximal fluvial and alluvial wash plains close to sites 1 and 2 as well as in the Saryesik-Atyrau dunefields.

2. OBJECTIVES

The over-arching goal of the project is a proof-of-concept study to investigate and validate the new quartz-ESR based provenance tool with more established geochemical and mineralogical methods. Towards this goal, we apply and test these different provenance determining methods for two different case-studies to explore aeolian dynamics in the Ili basin of SE Kazakhstan. It must be noted that for both the

case studies the ESR measurements on the quartz mineral were conducted previously by the author in her PhD thesis [16, 17].

(i) Case I: In the first case study, we investigate if concentrations of characteristic non-Si elemental impurities like Al and Ti in the quartz mineral (extracted from sediments) can distinguish different source areas in the Ili Basin. Further, we compare these results to ESR measurements on quartz from the same sedimentary quartz samples to assess its ability to differentiate between different surface sediments from across the Basin. The sedimentary samples used in this case study were obtained from different depositional areas in the Ili Basin that were previously identified as proximal source areas for modern dust in the piedmont regions of the Basin using dust-trajectory models [13].

(ii) Case II: The second case study aims to compare and validate the quartz based ESR provenance method with established geochemical provenance techniques (such Sr-Nd isotopes and rare-earth elements) on loess deposits in the piedmont regions of the Ili Basin. Such a multi-proxy provenance approach on loess sediments in this region also aims to provide reliable and well substantiated evidence for provenance change to better understand palaeowind dynamics in the Ili Basin through time. The loess samples used in this study were collected from two sites in the piedmonts of the Ili Basin (refer Fig. 1) that were previously dated using luminescence dating by the author in her PhD [17].

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Al and Ti elemental concentrations in individual Quartz grains

A suite of 28 coarse-grained quartz samples extracted from surface sediments were selected from different locations in the Ili Basin. The chosen samples are known to be potential contributors to the piedmont loess deposits in the Basin as inferred from data-driven dust trajectory models for the region [13]. For each sample, we analysed the Al and Ti concentration for five individual quartz grains using Joel JXA-8239 Electron Microprobe Microanalyser (EPMA) at the University of Tuebingen, Germany. The effective Al and Ti concentration was analysed at two different points on each grain, i.e., the centre and the rim of each grain. Therefore, a total of 10 measurements for Al and Ti were performed for each sample.

3.2. Sr-Nd isotopic analysis

We performed Sr-Nd isotopic analysis for three different grain size fractions (<11 μm , 63-212 μm and bulk) of 4 selected loess samples obtained from two different sites located in the piedmonts of the Tien Shan range-front in SE Kazakhstan. In total, 12 samples were analysed for Sr and Nd isotopic composition. The sample preparation for Sr and Nd analysis in the sediment fractions was performed as per standard protocols [e.g. 18] and the samples were measured using a thermal ionisation Mass spectrometer (Finnigan MAT262) at the Research group of Isotope Geochemistry at the University of Tuebingen, Germany.

3.3. Trace and Rare earth element (REE) analysis

We first analysed the trace and rare earth elemental composition of the same 4 samples (each with three different grain size fractions) as done previously in the case of Sr-Nd isotopic analysis. Based on the results of the Sr-Nd isotopic composition as well as REE analysis, we performed the trace and REE analysis for 21 loess samples for two sites in the Ili Basin. In the latter case, we only analysed the fine-grain sediment fraction (<11 μm) for each sample. The sample preparation for trace and REE's was conducted as per standard protocols [e.g. 19] and the measurements were performed using a iCAP Qc quadrupole ICP-MS at the Research group of Isotope Geochemistry at the University of Tuebingen, Germany.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Case I: Modern aeolian transport dynamics in the Ili Basin – Comparison of Quartz mineralogy (Al and Ti) with ESR-resolvable defect centres in quartz

The preliminary results on effective Al and Ti concentrations measured as AlO_2 and TiO_2 (wt %) respectively on 28 coarse-grained quartz samples extracted from rocks and sediments from the Ili Basin are shown in Fig. 2. Further, Fig. 2 (b) shows that the effective Al and Ti concentrations in individual quartz grains of a sample are mostly spread across the 0-0.02 (wt%) and 0-0.2 (wt%) for Ti and Al respectively, and this represents more than 95% of the data which overlaps with each other in this region. In addition, Fig. 3 shows that majority of the measurements lie below the detection limit for Al and Ti concentrations measured using EPMA and hence cannot be used reliably to differentiate between the different samples. This preliminary analysis of the Al and Ti concentrations of the quartz samples did not yield any affirmative results and hence we decided to discontinue this approach. A possible approach for future work will consider using LA-ICP MS (Laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass Spectrometry) analysis for its lower detection limit.

Figure 2. (a) Plot of AlO_2 (wt%) versus TiO_2 (wt %) from coarse-grained quartz using EPMA. (b) Magnified cross-plot of AlO_2 and TiO_2 (wt %) to better depict the variability in AlO_2 (wt%) for quartz grains in the lower range.

Figure 3. This plot shows all the data for effective Al and Ti concentrations measured as AlO_2 and TiO_2 (wt %) that lies below the detection limit (red-shaded area) of the EPMA. Note that this plot shows the data for AlO_2 within the range 0 - 0.20 wt %, as >95% of the data obtained lies within this range.

4.2. Case II: Aeolian dynamics in the Ili Basin in the past – Comparison of sediment geochemistry with ESR-resolvable defect centres in quartz

We performed Sr-Nd isotopic analysis as well as REE analysis for loess sediments in two steps. In the first step, we performed this geochemical analysis for a set of 4 selected samples with three different grain size fractions (<11 μm , 63-212 μm and bulk) for each of the samples. Fig. 4 (Sr-Nd isotopic ratios) and Fig. 5 (depicting chondrite normalised REE patterns) show that in most cases the bulk sediment signatures are closer to the fine fraction (<11 μm), suggesting that the bulk of the loess sediment is dominated by the finer component. Previous studies on the application of Sr and Nd isotopes on bulk sediment from loess profiles has shown that the Sr signature is affected by weathering and also depends on grain-size [7, 20]. This can also be observed for one of our samples (Fig. 4(a), A0017) where the Sr signature for the fine-fraction is more radiogenic compared to the other fractions from the same sample, as this sample was collected from the upper part of the loess profile (c. 50 cm from the top of the profile) and may be affected by soil forming processes (weathering and/or leaching processes, leading to enrichment and/or depletion of different mineral phases in the soil). While the Nd signature remains largely unaffected.

Figure 4. Variation of (a) $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ and (b) $\epsilon(0)$, where $\epsilon(0) = [(^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd}) / (^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd})_{\text{CHUR}}] * 10000$ for three different grain-size fractions obtained from 4 loess sediments.

On the other hand, Fig. 5(a-d) shows that the bulk and fine fraction REE patterns coincide really well, suggesting that the loess sediment is dominated largely by finer silty material, which also agrees with the grain size variations observed for these sites [refer 17]. Therefore, the preliminary results from REE analysis suggests that it is suitable for application to the finer sedimentary fraction of loess sediments and show minimal alteration due to weathering and was therefore used for all further analysis.

In the second step, we performed trace and REE analysis for the <11 μm sediment fraction of all the 21 loess samples collected from two loess profiles spanning the last glacial maximum in the Ili Basin. In this report, we present the most relevant data from the REE analysis. Since the two loess profiles lie in close proximity to each other (c. 30 Km) and temporally overlap with each other to span the past c.5-18 ka [17], we evaluate the data by grouping the samples based on whether they span the *Holocene* or *pre-Holocene*. This allows us to focus on temporal variations in provenance at these sites. Previous studies [21-23] on REE distribution patterns in loess suggest that REE's do not show fractionation during weathering events (e.g., in palaeosol units). However, Gallet et al [24] observed distinct Ce anomalies (Ce/Ce* ratios) in the palaeosol layers indicating the loss of Ce due to strong pedogenesis (strong reducing conditions) during

the interglacial periods. However, later studies reported that this was only observed in cases of strong weathering conditions (e.g. red soil formation in Southern China). In our samples, the Ce anomalies (Ce/Ce* ratios) are close to unity for all the samples as seen in Fig. 6(b). The Eu anomalies (Eu/Eu* ratio) for our samples range between 0.63-0.66 (<1, a negative anomaly) which is similar to that obtained for most loess samples in Central and East Asia [22-24], suggesting that the loess material is sourced from felsic sources derived from surrounding granitic and metasedimentary rocks. Fig. 6(c,d) shows some of the cross plots of the commonly used REE ratios La_N/Sm_N , Gd_N/Yb_N and La_N/Gd_N used as indicators of provenance or environmental changes in loess sediments [e.g. 22, 23]. The preliminary results obtained from these different ratios exhibits discernible differences between loess deposited during the Holocene and the pre-Holocene period across the two sites. Furthermore, the overlap in the E_1' signals from fine-grained quartz as well as the REE ratios of fine sediments for both sites (1 and 2) during the pre-Holocene periods as shown in all provenance markers across Fig. 6(a-d) assures us of the reproducibility and reliability of our results. The overall results from the REE ratios also corroborate with the change observed in the E' centres in quartz (refer Fig. 6(a)), thus providing independent validation to the application of E_1' centre (and peroxy centres) in quartz provenance studies.

Figure 5. (a-d). Chondrite normalised REE distribution patterns for three different grain-size fractions extracted from 4 loess samples.

Figure 6. Variation in (a) E_1' centres in fine grain (4-11 μm) quartz (b) Ce and Eu anomalies (Ce/Ce^* and Eu/Eu^* ratios respectively) and cross plot of (c) La_N/Sm_N vs Gd_N/Yb_N and (d) La_N/Gd_N vs La_N/Sm_N for <11 μm sediment fraction extracted from 21 loess samples from 2 loess sites spanning the past 18 ka.

5. Conclusions and Future Outlook

This pilot study was aimed at validating the ESR based provenance method on quartz with established geochemical and mineralogical techniques and at the same time address two main questions on aeolian dynamics in the Ili Basin. *First*, can we quantitatively link proximal surface samples to modern (surface) loess deposits along the Tien Shan range-front, as previously established by dust-transport models? *Second*, can we quantitatively assess change in provenance of sediments from loess deposits through time within the same Basin? Our first case study on preliminary mineralogical investigations on quartz extracted from different surface sediments in the Ili Basin did not yield any conclusive results as the Al and Ti content of the majority of quartz grains was below the detection limit of the EPMA. However, for the second case study, we were able to successfully validate the novel ESR based provenance method using E_1' (and peroxy) centres in quartz with more established geochemical provenance techniques based on REE ratios to better understand past aeolian dynamics in the Ili Basin. The application of both these

methods to loess profiles in SE Kazakhstan was able to distinguish between loess deposited in the Holocene period from that deposited during the pre-Holocene period. The change in provenance observed at the transition from the Holocene to the deglacial period corroborates with climate simulation studies [25] which suggest that the strength of the Siberian High was reduced at this time, leading to a relatively increased influence of the Westerlies in the Ili Basin.

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